

Mathematical knowledge for teaching: focus on Specialized Content Knowledge (SCK) of calculus class

Ahmed Ibrahim Usman*,

Department of General Studies, Jubail University College,
Jubail Industrial City, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Received: 27 Mar 2021

•

Accepted: 27 Apr 2021

•

Published Online: 30 Apr 2021

Abstract: The components of teachers' knowledge have been widely conceptualized since the advent of Shulman's teacher knowledge categorization in mid-1980s. It was widely acknowledged that the effectiveness of teachers and the success of their students' rely on the strength of their subject matter content knowledge. Based on this perspective, many teacher knowledge models were developed. This paper appraised the Specialized Content Knowledge (SCK) with particular reference to Calculus. SCK is a sub-domain of Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching (MKT). MKT is a required skill and expertise of mathematics that is particularly essential to a successful instruction. SCK and its relevance were examined and reported with specific focus to the teaching of Calculus at Jubail University College.

Key words: Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching, Special Content Knowledge, Mathematical Tasks for teaching, Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus.

1. Introduction

The relationship between teaching and learning has been widely researched since the antiquity. The focus was on their typologies, which are mostly ideological (behaviorism, constructivism, etc.), applicability in classes of other situation and challenges (funding, overcrowded classes, etc.). After Shulman's discovery of pedagogical content knowledge in the mid-1980s, research trajectory changed. Focus shifted to subject matter content knowledge of teachers on what they should have known in order to teach or are planning to teach at any level, i.e. elementary school, secondary school and tertiary level. There is a widespread agreement among mathematics educators' community in particular and teacher education communities in general that teachers' mathematical knowledge has an overwhelming influence on teaching and learning as well as students' success, [6]. Attaining this height of prosperity requires mathematics teachers to have a sound knowledge of mathematics subject matter. Furthermore, mathematics teachers should have immersed ability of inter connectivity among different areas of mathematics specialty as well as with other applicable fields, [1, 5, 10].

2. Domain of Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching (MKT)

Phelps and Howell (2016), citing [1, 2], submitted that MKT "is the content knowledge used in recognizing, understanding, and responding to the mathematical problems and tasks encountered in teaching the subject" (page 52). Based on the domain mapping 1 above, MKT is composed of mathematics knowledge that includes several types of content knowledge: Common Content Knowledge (CCK), Specialized Content Knowledge (SCK) and Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK). SCK is a mathematical skill and knowledge particularly required

Figure 1. Domain map for mathematical knowledge for teaching(Hill, Ball & Schilling, 2008)

in teaching. There are some supporting mathematical tasks for teaching proposed by Ball et al. that can be used to reinforce SCK. In this paper, those tasks were used to appraise SCK domain of professional mathematics teachers’ calculus classroom session.

3. Mathematical Tasks of Teaching

Ball, Thames, and Phelps (2008) [1] stated that teachers routinely use several mathematical tasks of teaching that are sometimes spontaneous. These tasks were required for a successful teaching of Mathematics. Five Mathematical tasks of teaching are considered among several other tasks.

- Presenting Mathematical Ideas
- Responding to students’ ‘WHY’ questions
- Connecting a topic being taught to topics from prior or future years.pic
- Modify tasks to be either easier or harder
- Evaluating the plausibility of students’ claims (often quickly)

4. Appraising SCK Mathematical Tasks and its Relevance in Teaching Calculus Presenting Mathematical Ideas

The first mathematical idea to be presented as a sample from many SCK mathematical tasks is Differential Calculus. Under this, the general idea of Calculus is presented logically in the following way.

Differential Calculus is a branch of mathematics that deals with continuously varying quantities. It is used to compute the concepts of rates of changes, slopes of curves. It is the study of rates of changes such as real life phenomena. It describes how quantities change. In geometry, Differential Calculus (derivative) is related with the concept of tangent line to a curve. The idea of a tangent line to a curve and methods for finding its slope and equation are used to generate the definition of derivatives.

Considering the diagram in Figure 2, let A be a point in a curve determined by the equation $y = f(x)$, and AT the tangent line at A. Let $OE = x, DA = y$. If x increases by Δx and y increases by Δy

$$\text{Then, } \tan BAC = \frac{BC}{AB} = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}.$$

Figure 2. Tangent

If Δx shrinks and approaches zero, then, Δy will also approach zero. The point B will move along the curve towards A , AB will approach the direction of AT as its limit.

$$\tan TAB = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{dy}{dx} \quad (1)$$

That is, the derivative dy/dx , at any point of a curve, is the trigonometric tangent of the angle of inclination to the x -axis of the tangent line at that point. This measure is denoted by the term slope. The slope of a straight line is the tangent of its angle of inclination to the x -axis. Thus, dy/dx (rate of change of y with respect to x) at any point of a curve, is the slope of the curve at that point. Furthermore, the change in y divided by the change in x varies as we move along the curve.

If a function is linear (i.e. if the graph of the function is a straight line), then the function can be written as $y = mx + c$, where m is the slope of the straight line, x is the independent variable, y is the dependent variable, and c is the y -intercept. Thus, the slope of a straight line.

$$m = \frac{\text{rise}}{\text{run}} = \frac{\text{change in } y}{\text{change in } x} = \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}$$

This gives an exact value for the slope of a straight line.

In general, let $y = f(x)$, if x increases by Δx , and y increases by Δy , thus the new value is:

$$y + \Delta y = f(x + \Delta x) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta y = f(x + \Delta x) - f(x) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{f(x + \Delta x) - f(x)}{\Delta x} \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} = \frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x + \Delta x) - f(x)}{\Delta x} \quad (4)$$

If Δx is replaced by h , a formal definition of derivative of a function f with respect to x is given by the formula $f' = \frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h}$.

An example is used to illustrate the limit definition of derivative. Find the derivation of the function, $y = 3x^2 + 5x - 7$

$$\text{Let } f = y = 3x^2 + 5x - 7$$

$$f' = \frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{3(x+h)^2 + 5(x+h) - 7 - (3x^2 + 5x - 7)}{h} \tag{5}$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{3(x^2 + 2xh + h^2) + 5(x+h) - 7 - (3x^2 + 5x - 7)}{h} \tag{6}$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{3x^2 + 6xh + 3h^2 + 5x + 5h - 7 - 3x^2 - 5x + 7}{h} \tag{7}$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{6xh + 3h^2 + 5h}{h} = 6x + 5. \tag{8}$$

4.1. Responding to Students’ “Why” Questions

In the process of teaching a topic in mathematics at any level, teachers are faced with challenges of answering students’ “why” questions. Such questions usually come up spontaneously in circumstantial situations, especially in lower level classes. An example of such situation explaining why

$$-\ln |\cos x| = \ln |\sec x| \tag{9}$$

In trying to answer this “why” question, the teacher needs to explain to the students as quickly as possible using the properties of logarithm/natural logarithm, law of indices, and trigonometric identities.

Another example of “why” question is given below

$$e^{\ln \sin x} = \sin x \quad \text{and} \quad e^{\ln \tan x} = \tan x = \frac{\sin x}{\cos x}.$$

In an attempt to simplify the expression that may recur in class discussion or presentation, the teacher comes up with explanation on the inverse relationship between exponential and natural logarithmic (logarithm base e) functions as well as trigonometric identity.

In teaching Calculus and other Mathematics courses, it is very likely that the given “why” expression in exponential law $x^0 = 1, x \neq 0$ would come up.

This law could best be explained using another exponential law $\frac{x^a}{x^b} = x^{a-b}$ numerically. Quickly, the given example could be used. Simplify the expression, $\frac{x^3}{x^3} = \frac{x \cdot x \cdot x}{x \cdot x \cdot x} = \frac{1}{1} = 1 \dots \dots \dots (1)$. On the other side, using the exponential law, $\frac{x^3}{x^3} = x^{(3-3)} = x^0 \dots \dots \dots (2)$. Equating equations (1) and (2) give a simple explanation of why $x^0 = 1$.

4.2. Connecting a Topic being Taught to Topics from Prior or Future years

One of the major challenges Mathematics teachers (Calculus teachers, in particular) are facing is trying to make connections between previous or future topic(s) with current topic(s). Below are some examples: The teacher should establish a connection between Difference Quotient $\frac{f(x+h)-f(x)}{h}$ in College Algebra (Larson, 2018) and using difference quotient in finding slope/tangent/average rate of change in Differential Calculus as given below,

$$f' = \frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x+h) - f(x)}{h}.$$

Another instance of attempting to make connection with the current topic is Chain Rule technique of differentiating a function in Differential Calculus and Composition of Functions in College Algebra. Example, the composition of two functions

$$f \text{ and } g \text{ is given as } (f \circ g)(x) = f(g(x)), (Larson, 2018).$$

This concept could be linked with the Chain Rule techniques of differentiating functions in Differential Calculus. Example, the derivative of

$$(f \circ g)'(x) = f'(g(x))g'(x).$$

The teacher establishes this connection to help students better understand Chain Rule techniques of differentiation by helping them recall the Composition of Functions from College Algebra.

Within Calculus, there are a lot of connectivity between topics. One such situation is Chain Rule technique of differentiation and substitution method in Integral Calculus. Teachers should establish this relationship as early as possible. Drawing students' attention to this connection would help in keeping their concentration in learning the Chain Rule technique of Differential Calculus.

Example, use the chain rule to find the derivative of the function, (Thomas, 2016)

$$h(x) = \sin(x^3 - 2e^x); h'(x) = \cos(x^3 - 2e^x)(3x^2 - 2e^x)$$

If $h(x) = (f \circ g)(x) = f(g(x))$, then $h'(x) = f'(g(x))g'(x)$, using the Chain Rule. From the above example, $g(x) = x^3 - 2e^x$ is an inside function, while $f(x) = \sin x$ is the outside function. The derivative of h is given by multiplying the derivative of the outside function and the derivative of inside function, i.e. $h'(x) = \cos(x^3 - 2e^x)(3x^2 - 2e^x)$

Conversely, using substitution technique, if $u = g(x)$ is a differentiable function on an interval I and f is also continuous on I , then

$$\int f(g(x))g'(x)dx = \int f(u)du$$

Example,

$$\int \cos(x^3 - 2e^x)(3x^2 - 2e^x)dx$$

Let $u = x^3 - 2e^x$, then $du/dx = 3x^2 - 2e^x \rightarrow du = (3x^2 - 2e^x)dx$

therefore $\int \cos(x^3 - 2e^x)(3x^2 - 2e^x)dx = \int \cos u du = \sin u + C = \sin(x^3 - 2e^x) + C$

It is a very common saying that College Algebra and Trigonometry are gate keepers that prevent students from registering for Differential and Integral Calculus courses very early, as required by their majors usually in Bachelor degree programs. One common content of trigonometry required in either Differential or Integral Calculus is trigonometric identities.

The sum and difference formulas in trigonometry are used to find the derivatives of sine and cosine functions. Example,

$$\sin(A + B) = \sin A \cos B + \cos A \sin B \text{ as well as } \cos(A + B) = \cos A \cos B - \sin A \sin B$$

Similarly, the derivatives of other trigonometric functions of tangent, secant, cotangent and cosecant are found using trigonometric ratio/quotient identities as well as quotient rule of differentiation. Example, the derivative of tangent function, $\frac{d}{dx}(\tan x) = \frac{d}{dx}(\sin x / \cos x)$. Subsequently, quotient rule would then be used to find the required derivative. In Integral Calculus, double angle formula and other trigonometric identities are used tremendously. The teacher should point out to the students that power rule techniques of integrating algebraic function will not be applicable to trigonometric functions. Example, the integration of $\sin^2 x$ and $\cos^2 x$ are found using appropriate trigonometric identities, i.e.

$$\sin^2 x = \frac{1 - \cos 2x}{2} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos 2x) \text{ , and } \cos^2 x = \frac{1 + \cos 2x}{2} = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos 2x)$$

Similarly, the teacher should emphasize that other powers of sine and cosine are found using suitable trigonometric identities from College Algebra and Trigonometry classes.

On a cumulative basis, at the university level, especially in Jubail University College, Mathematics courses are taken as a sequence, i.e. College Algebra and Trigonometry, Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus, Multi-variable Calculus and Elements of Differential Equations for computer science and engineering students. It is pertinent for a teacher to emphasize the importance and applicability of every topic taught at lower levels to successfully tackle the challenges students face in Elements of Differential Equation. For example, in the process of solving a differential equations problem, a student comes across

$$\int e^{2 \ln \sin x} dx = \int e^{\ln \sin^2 x} dx = \int \sin^2 x dx \leftarrow \int \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos 2x).$$

In this process, logarithmic laws, inverse relationship between exponential and natural logarithm function, trigonometric identities as well as integration of trigonometric functions are used in a single problem. There are many such situations that require fundamental application of concepts from College Algebra and Trigonometry, Differential and Integral Calculus to solve a single differential equations problem.

4.3. Modify Tasks to be either Easier or Harder

In teaching Calculus, there are a lot of situations where examples are presented to further explain the concepts already introduced. It is a good idea for teachers to start from the known (easy) examples to the unknown (harder) ones. Following are some examples to support this strategy: Use implicit differentiation to find $\frac{dy}{dx}$ if $x^2 \ln y = 10$ (This problem is an easy one with clear direction.)

$$x^2 \frac{1}{y} \frac{dy}{dx} + 2x \ln y = 0$$

$$\frac{x^2}{y} \frac{dy}{dx} = -2x \ln y$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{-2y}{x} \ln y$$

A second example follows as: Find the derivative, i.e. $\frac{d}{dx}((\csc x \sin x) / \cos x)$. This example looks harder, without simplification.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\csc x \sin x}{\cos x} \right) \rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\frac{1}{\sin x} \sin x}{\cos x} \right) \rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} \frac{1}{\cos x} \rightarrow \frac{d}{dx} (\cos x)^{-1}$$

After lowest simplification, Chain Rule is used to find the derivative.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx}(\cos x)^{-1} &= -(\cos x)^{-2} \frac{d}{dx} \cos x \rightarrow -(\cos x)^{-2}(-\sin x) \\ (\cos x)^{-2}(\sin x) &\rightarrow \frac{\sin x}{(\cos x)^2} \rightarrow \frac{\sin x}{\cos x} \frac{1}{\cos x} \rightarrow \tan x \sec x \end{aligned}$$

Another example is an applied question with no clear direction, i.e. (specified method). A point p is moving along a curve whose equation is $y = \sqrt{(x^2 + 1600)}$, When $(9, 41)$. y is increasing at a rate of 2 units/s. How fast is x changing?

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = \frac{x}{\sqrt{(x^2 + 1600)}} \frac{dx}{dt}$$

From the given problem, $\frac{dy}{dt} = 2$, $x = 9$, and $\frac{dx}{dt} = ?$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= \frac{\frac{dy}{dt} \sqrt{(x^2 + 1600)}}{x} \\ \frac{dx}{dt} &= \frac{2 \cdot \sqrt{(9^2 + 1600)}}{9} \rightarrow \frac{82}{9} = 9.11 \\ \frac{dx}{dt} &= 9.11 \text{ units/s} \end{aligned}$$

x is changing at 9.11 units per second.

4.4. Evaluating the Plausibility of Students' Claims (often quickly)

Major sources of plausibility are mostly from algebraic law of indices, logarithmic properties, and trigonometric identities. This plausibility crops up spontaneously in teaching Differential and Integral Calculus.

Some examples from algebraic laws of indices are:

$a^{\frac{x}{y}} = \sqrt[y]{a^x} = (\sqrt[y]{a})^x$, $(a^n)^m = a^{n \cdot m}$, $\sqrt[n]{ab} = \sqrt[n]{a} \sqrt[n]{b}$, $\sqrt[n]{\frac{a}{b}} = \frac{\sqrt[n]{a}}{\sqrt[n]{b}}$ and so on, (Larson, 2018). Expression involving these terms appears spontaneously and regularly in steps and procedures of solving Differential and Integral Calculus. Similarly, some common logarithmic properties constantly recurring in Differential and Integral Calculus are.

$$\begin{aligned} \log_a(xy) &= \log_a(x) + \log_a(y); \\ \log_a\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) &= \log_a(x) - \log_a(y); \\ p \log_a(x) &= \log_a(x)^p \\ \log_a(x) &= \frac{\ln x}{\ln a} \end{aligned}$$

Another group of common source of plausibility is coming from basic trigonometric identities. A few are stated below:

$$\begin{aligned} \sin^2 x + \cos^2 x &= 1 \\ 1 + \cot^2 x &= \operatorname{cosec}^2 x \\ \sin 2x &= 2 \sin x \cos x \text{ (from trigonometric addition rule)} \\ \cos 2x &= \cos^2 x - \sin^2 x \\ \cos 2x &= 2 \cos^2 x - 1 \\ \cos 2x &= 1 - \operatorname{fr}m\text{-}e\sin^2 x . \end{aligned}$$

Teachers should explain these identities to the students as quickly as possible, whenever the need arises.

4.5. Selecting Representations for Particular Purposes

In these mathematical tasks, two solutions would be presented for a single problem, each from a different representation.

The first is using geometric representation. Using this approach, find the solution of the problem

$$\int_{-3}^3 \sqrt{9-x^2} dx = \frac{9\pi}{2} \text{ square units}$$

sketching a circle of radius 3 units, and finding its area using geometric formula. The area of the whole circle is $A = \pi r^2 \rightarrow \pi 3^2 = 9\pi$ square units. The required area under the curve $y = \sqrt{9-x^2}$, and interval $[-3, 3]$, is an area of a semicircle and its area is $\frac{9\pi}{2}$ square units.

The second approach is using trigonometric substitution, i.e. transforming algebraic representation to trigonometric form.

$$\int_{-3}^3 \sqrt{9-x^2} dx, \text{ Let } x = a \sin \theta \rightarrow x = 3 \sin \theta, dx = 3 \cos \theta d\theta, \text{ and } x^2 = 9 \sin^2 \theta$$

Similarly, changing the limits gives $x = -3, \theta = -\pi/2$, and when $x = 3, \theta = \pi/2$

$$\int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \sqrt{9 - \sin^2 \theta} 3 \cos \theta d\theta = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} 9 \cos^2 \theta d\theta$$

$$\int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} 9 \cos^2 \theta d\theta \rightarrow \frac{9}{2} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} (\cos 2\theta + 1) d\theta \rightarrow \frac{9}{2} \left[\frac{\sin 2\theta}{2} + \theta \right]_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \rightarrow \frac{9\pi}{2} \text{ square units}$$

Teacher should explain to the students how using different representations to solve a particular problem lead to a consistent solution.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

MKT and SCK are indispensable tools for the successful teaching of Mathematics in general, Differential and Integral Calculus in particular. Teachers with sound mathematical knowledge for teaching Differential and Integral Calculus will be able to give detailed and clear explanations on concepts and terms of Differential and Integral Calculus to students. They should be able to give solutions of a particular problem using different representations accurately. Also, they should be able to help students interpret and judge their solutions using examples and counter examples. The teachers should have the ability to explain the progression of Differential and Integral Calculus lessons conceptually as well as sequentially using appropriate procedures. Model Differential and Integral Calculus teachers should be able to encourage students to ask questions based on the concepts presented. Similarly, they should probe students' answers immediately to ensure they have really grasped the topic imparted. In every Mathematics course(s) or topic(s) taught, teachers might be confronted with enormous difficulties from the students. In particular, Differential and Integral Calculus teachers in any university are faced with serious questions. Consequently, the need to be well prepared and up to the task. One major area of concern to the teachers is students' previous knowledge in College Algebra and Trigonometry, which is a pre-requisite of Differential and Integral Calculus. This is considered an important and essential tool. Another area of concern to teachers is students' incompetence in following conceptual and procedural paces of the solutions of Differential and Integral Calculus logically. In a similar note, students' overall mathematical proficiency is an added area of apprehension. Finally, nowadays, students tend to care more about their grades than paying attention to learning concepts and application Differential and Integral Calculus.

References

- [1] Ball, D. L., Thames, M. H., & Phelps, G. (2008). Content knowledge for teaching: What makes it special? *Journal of Teacher Education*, 59(5), 389 – 407.
- [2] Ball, D. L., & Bass, H. (2002). Toward a practice-based theory of mathematical Knowledge for teaching. In *Proceedings of the 2002 annual meeting of the Canadian Mathematics Education Study Group*, 3 – 14.
- [3] Hill, H. C., Rowan, B., & Ball, D. L. (2005). Effects of teachers' mathematical Knowledge for teaching on students' achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*. 42(2), 371 – 406.
- [4] Larson, R., (2018). *Algebra and Trigonometry with CalcChat and CalcView*, 10th Edition, Boston, MA, Cengage Learning.
- [5] Ma, L., (1999). *Knowing and Teaching Elementary School Mathematics*. Mahwah, NJ, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [6] NMAP (2008). *Foundation for success. The Final Report of the National Mathematics Advisory Panel*. U.S. Department of Education.
- [7] Phelps, G., & Howell, H. (2016). Assessing Mathematical Knowledge for Teaching: The Role of Teaching Context. *The Mathematics Enthusiast*. 13(1 & 2), 52 – 70.
- [8] Shulman, L. S. (1986). Those who understand, knowledge growth in teaching, *Educational Researcher*, 15(2), 4 – 14.
- [9] Thomas, G. B., (2016). *Thomas's Calculus Early Transcendentals*, 13th Edition. Essex, England. Pearson Educational Limited.
- [10] Three P(3P) – Learning (2021). How to Factor the Real World into the Mathematics Teaching Equation. 3P Learning – The teaching moments that inspire learning, <https://www.mathletics.com/blog/educators/how-to-factor-the-real-world-into-the-mathematics-teaching-equation/> ((retrieved on 10-01-2021))